

Summary

This report, commissioned by Open Science NL and the Dutch Research Agenda (NWA) (both part of the Dutch Research Council NWO), is the result of a study into the preconditions for equal collaboration between citizen scientists and participatory researchers and makes concrete recommendations to NWO to facilitate this. This study was conducted by TwynstraGudde between September 2024 and September 2025. The results are based on three social lab meetings, a desk study, interviews with experts and a survey.

Recommendations include setting up a separate funding programme for bottom-up participatory research and long-term funding, investing in capacity building, and recognising and meeting the different needs of citizen scientists. In addition, concrete suggestions are made for implementing these recommendations: a clear vision, continuous learning, and evaluating the participatory approach.

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Summary	2
1. Introduction	4
2. Theoretical framework	6
3. Methods	9
4. Analysis	11
5. Recommendations	13

1. Introduction

Citizen science and other participatory forms of research have a rich history and are developing rapidly both within and outside the Netherlands.¹ There are many definitions of citizen science². For the purposes of this report, we define citizen science as scientific research in which people outside the academic world, i.e. citizens, are actively involved. **Patients, clients, relatives, professionals and policymakers can also be actively involved in research. To emphasise their active involvement, we refer to them as 'citizen scientists' and the research that is set up and carried out together as 'participatory research'.**

The involvement of citizen scientists can be organised in different phases within research. This includes setting the research agenda, co-designing the conditions of funding programmes, as well as carrying out and communicating (dissemination) about the research in order to achieve high-quality participatory research/citizen science.

In participatory research, equality is desirable: recognising the fact that power imbalances often exist or can arise within research projects.³ Certainly in lighter forms of citizen science, citizen scientists are still too often seen as potential sensors rather than full-fledged research partners. Academic researchers are often in charge of research projects. They set up the project and carry it out. Involving citizen scientists in research projects led by researchers can lead to misunderstandings and unequal influence. Citizen scientists often do not feel like equal partners. Incidentally, this is a situation that does not only occur in consortia in which citizens participate. In consortia in which researchers from different domains, governments and civil society organisations, or companies (e.g. public-private partnerships) work together, unequal timelines, different uses of concepts and unequal relationships can complicate cooperation.

Open Science NL and the National Research Agenda (both part of the Dutch Research Council NWO) asked TwynstraGudde to investigate the preconditions under which citizen scientists can collaborate more equally with researchers in research projects. This leads to the following main question:

Under what conditions can citizen(s) and researchers collaborate on a (more) equal footing in research projects?

NWO has indicated to us that they are also interested in the question of what is needed in the development process of a programme, which stakeholders should be involved and what support is needed for this. Furthermore, NWO wants to explore whether and how a targeted funding programme for participatory research can be set up within NWO, taking into account as many needs and conditions as possible.

¹ Dekker, T., Kuijpers, E., & Lenarduzzi, C. (2023). From crowdsourcing to real citizen science: Invest in the quality of collaboration. *City History*, 18(2).

² Haklay, M., Dörler, D., Heigl, F., Manzoni, M., Hecker, S., & Vohland, K. (2021). What is citizen science? The challenges of definition. *The science of citizen science*.

³<https://www.rathenau.nl/nl/kennis-en-innovatie-voor-transities/opgavegericht-kennis-en-innovatiebeleid/wees-je-bewust-van-macht>

In an initial interim report (report 1), we reported on the results of fifteen interviews and a desk study on this subject.⁴ The results of the social lab process are described in a second report (report 2).⁵ This document contains the recommendations we make based on these two reports. In the next chapter, we first outline the theoretical framework we used. We then describe the methodology used. In the following chapter, we describe the results of the *social labs* phase. We conclude with our recommendations and a preview of the follow-up process.

NB: Open Science NL works in close consultation with stakeholders involved in the Dutch Research Agenda (NWA). A parallel process is under way to identify existing citizen science and participation activities within funded NWA projects. For this reason, projects from NWA have been excluded from this specific study.

⁴ Cohen, J. B., de Sterke, P., & Pulskens, B. (2025). Diagnosis report Preliminary phase Citizen Science (in Dutch). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15497402>

⁵ Pulskens, B., Cohen, J. B. & de Sterke, P., (2025). Social Labs Report Preliminary Phase Citizen Science (in Dutch). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17100284>

2. Theoretical framework

In our first report we have established what we mean by **equality** in cooperation.

For us, equality is about taking into account the identity and the background of people in such a way that they are able to participate in a collaborative process.⁶ It is important that everyone's input and perspective is recognised and taken seriously, so that everyone can influence decisions and outcomes. This is different from striving for complete equality. We also talk about the difference between *equity* and *equality*:

Equity is an approach that recognises that the magnitude of systemic barriers posed to a particular person will vary based on their [background]. Equity recognises that different people will need different amounts of resources or support in order to succeed and overcome these barriers. It is important to note that equity is different than equality, because equality-based approaches assume that everyone should be treated the same.^{7 8}

As described in the first report, we use our 'framework for collaboration' to determine the **preconditions for equal collaboration**. We focus on four preconditions that must be met in order for a cooperation to operate successfully on an equal footing.

- *Motivation: why are we working together?*
- *The organisation: how do we work together (structure/hard)?*
- *Interaction: how do we work together (culture/soft)?*
- *The realisation: what does the collaboration deliver?*

⁶<https://codedi.nl/gelijkheid-versus-gelijkwaardigheid-hoe-verhouden-ze-zich-tot-diversiteit-inclusie>

⁷<https://sparcopen.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Diversity-Equity-and-Inclusion-Report-July-10-V1-Release.pdf>

⁸ See also Minow, M. (2021). Equality vs. equity. *American Journal of Law and Equality*, 1, 167-193 for a comprehensive and nuanced discussion of the different concepts, their history and their contemporary use.

Figure 1 – ‘Framework for collaboration’

In the first report, based on a desk study and interviews, we found that attention to these four aspects is crucial for bringing about good and equal collaboration. A summary of these findings is presented below.

Summary of the first report

Motivation: Potentially, equitable participatory research can contribute to the democratisation of science, to better research results and to greater trust in science. The motivation for collaboration in participatory research differs greatly. Motivations can range from selfish and altruistic drives to more collectivist and principled motives. Recognising and appreciating these motivations in a timely manner can help to make the collaboration sustainable.

Organisation: Successful collaboration requires a deliberate strategy, a clear organisational structure and sufficient support and funding. Flexible and open funding programmes are essential to involve different participants on an equal footing. There is a need to recognise voluntary efforts and reimburse expenses for citizen scientists. Funders play a crucial role in creating innovative funding programmes and in sharing knowledge about best practices.

Interaction: Equal collaboration depends on clearly expressed interests, on valuing differences and a sense of equality. Training and networking are crucial for strengthening these soft factors. It is important to overcome barriers arising from power differences and prejudices between different groups. Organising meetings, involving diverse people (for example children through their schools) and lowering the threshold for participation can contribute to more equal collaboration.

Realisation: *The success of collaboration must be visible and meaningful, with attention to monitoring, reflection and flexibility. It is important to celebrate results and recognise the added value of collaboration. Citizen science can contribute to better scientific results with more effective and impactful outcomes, social cohesion and greater trust in science. Creating a learning process, space for experimenting with new forms of funding, and continuity in the duration and organisation of the research are essential for sustainable collaboration.*

In the report, we concluded that equal collaboration in participatory research requires attention to the specific points mentioned above. By addressing these aspects, NWO can contribute to sustainable and meaningful collaborations between citizens and researchers.

This research thus offers several starting points for NWO to consider the funding and support of equal collaboration in participatory research. By better responding to the motivations of citizen scientists and sharing influence in the design and decision-making, NWO can contribute to more equal collaboration from the outset of programmes and projects.

3. Methods

The main objective of this study is to provide advice on the preconditions under which citizens (civic organisations) and researchers can collaborate more equally in research projects. These insights and information can help NWO to make informed choices. Participants in the study have an advisory role. The decision-making and implementation of the final advice lies with the Open Science NL Steering Board/NWA Programme Committee and the NWO Executive Board.

This report is based on input gathered during three *social lab* sessions and a survey.⁹ A social lab¹⁰ is an open methodology that enables researchers to study socially challenging topics in a participatory manner together with stakeholders and experts, while at the same time experimenting with prototypes and solutions in order to arrive at systemic recommendations. They provide a space for experimentation in *real-life settings*, bringing together different stakeholder groups in an interdisciplinary manner, with room for action at the micro level that can in turn provide lessons and insights for systemic change.¹¹ They are also iterative, with room for learning, adjustments and development throughout the process.¹²

During the **first workshop**, we presented our results from the first study and got to know the participants and their perspectives/motivations with regard to citizen science. We briefly presented the background and initial results of the process and asked participants to share their vision for the future of equal participatory research on a postcard and present it to each other. We then asked them to reflect in groups on the results presented (interviews and document study) in two rounds. First, we asked them to fill in ready-made templates and then to indicate what they thought was a) important, b) within their sphere of influence, and c) what they felt energised by. We then invited them to design mini-research projects themselves to further identify, test and validate conditions for equal collaboration in citizen science.

In the design of the **second workshop**, we provided space for feedback on the mini-research studies in order to further enrich and deepen the recommendations. We also explored the way in which participatory research is organised in the urban context of Rotterdam. In the afternoon, we split into groups based on four cases to reflect on which stakeholders could be involved. We also used the *Crazy 8s* method to identify creative ways to involve these stakeholders in four phases of scientific research funding. Finally, using a template, we worked in groups to develop recommendations for a funding programme for participatory research.

⁹ Pulskens, B., Cohen, J. B. & de Sterke, P., (2025). Social labs report Preliminary phase Citizen Science (in Dutch). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17100284>

¹⁰ Marschalek, I., Blok, V., Bernstein, M., Braun, R., Cohen, J., Hofer, M., ... & Kumar Thapa, R. (2022). The social lab as a method for experimental engagement in participatory research. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 9(3), 419-442.

¹¹ Cohen, J. B., Loeber, A. M., Marschalek, I., Bernstein, M. J., Blok, V., Tabarés, R., ... & Griessler, E. (2024). From experimentation to structural change: fostering institutional entrepreneurship for public engagement in research and innovation. *Science and Public Policy*, 51(2), 324-336.

¹² Braun, R., Loeber, A., Vinther Christensen, M., Cohen, J., Frankus, E., Griessler, E., ... & Starkbaum, J. (2023). Social labs as temporary intermediary learning organisations to help implement complex normative policies. The case of Responsible Research and Innovation in European science governance. *The Learning Organisation*, 30(6), 713-739.

In the design of the **third workshop**, we connected the results of the first two workshops and the survey. We also shared a draft of the advice with the attendees for review and feedback. In the afternoon session, we drew inspiration from the local Twente context and followed a 'dream assignment'¹³ to generate visions of the future for equal collaboration within participatory research. Based on these visions of the future, we identified values that are important for achieving this future and also raised ideas about the role of NWO in bringing these visions of the future closer. In addition, we created a survey to also give other people the opportunity to provide input for the advice. We drew inspiration for the design of the survey from the 'framework on collaboration' and from the results of the interviews. We also shared the survey with the participants of the *social lab* for review and feedback. Three of them responded. We used their feedback to improve the survey. We then shared the survey with the help of Open Science NL, Citizen Science NL and Waag FutureLab.

¹³ This assignment is a combination of Merlijn Twaalfhoven's intervention De Goede Voorouder (The Good Ancestor) (see Janssen, A., Pulskens, B., Bongers, L., Barendrecht, T. and Hageman, J. (2024) *The Transition Guide. Practical interventions for social challenges*. Boom) and 'Take-a-panel', an exercise from the MG Taylor method for group intervention events, adapted by Pam de Sterke.

4. Analysis

The **first report**¹⁴ showed that there is considerable interest in promoting equal collaboration in participatory research both at home and abroad. In equal collaboration, attention should be paid to the motivations of those involved, the organisation of the collaboration (both structurally and culturally), the interaction within this collaboration, and the intended results that the collaboration should yield. The report provided several points of attention with regard to the funding and support of this type of collaboration. Some elements to take into account are:

- Organising both stepwise (phases) and long-term funding;
- Compensating contributions and costs of citizen scientists and building in flexibility in processes;
- Investing in networking, training, guidelines and skills, both for (citizen) researchers and assessment committees.

In addition, it became apparent that funders such as NWO need to take into account the different goals the various target groups wish to achieve. This requires a learning process and room to experiment with new forms of funding.

The recommendations in the first report were well received and published by Open Science NL in both Dutch and English. This provided sufficient starting points for further exploration in the Social Lab sessions and the survey.

The **social labs process**¹⁷ provided insights from the community of citizen scientists and participatory researchers on the following themes:

- Definitions of equality in participatory research and priorities of the findings from the first report;
- Insight into stakeholders in research and ways in which they can be involved in various phases of funding, as well as creating building blocks for the design of a specific funding programme aimed at equitable participatory research;
- Desired visions of the future of equal collaboration in participatory research with underlying values and principles, and insight into the necessary role and support of NWO in bringing this future closer.

The **survey** also revealed that there is broad consensus that participatory research benefits from a more bottom-up approach in which *'it should be more with the citizen than about the citizen'*. Ideally, citizen scientists should have a *significant or even the most influence on the funding* of participatory research and exert influence in all phases of the research. The degree of influence depends on the type of research and the extent to which citizens are affected by the subject. At the same time, not everyone wants to or is able to be involved to the same degree, and equality does not mean that everyone must fulfil the same role. It is also important to properly safeguard certain aspects, such as the quality of the research and ethical dimensions.

¹⁴ Cohen, J. B., de Sterke, P., & Pulskens, B. (2025). Diagnosis report Preliminary phase Citizen Science (in Dutch). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/15497402>

¹⁵ Cohen, J. B., de Sterke, P., & Pulskens, B. (2025). Diagnostic report Preliminary phase Citizen Science (in Dutch). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/15497402>

¹⁶ Cohen, J. B., de Sterke, P., & Pulskens, B. (2025). Diagnosis report Preliminary phase Citizen Science (in English). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/15703423>

¹⁷ Pulskens, B., Cohen, J. B. & de Sterke, P., (2025). Social Labs Report Preliminary Phase Citizen Science (in Dutch). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17100284>

In general, a wide range of barriers to participatory research are experienced, ranging from practical and structural to cultural obstacles. A recurring obstacle to equality, for example, is that knowledge institutions often occupy a dominant position in relation to citizen scientists, which puts equality under pressure. Better and more equal collaboration requires both formal support (such as funding) and informal support (such as training and networking).

When assessing projects, criteria such as *degree of involvement*, *impact on the target group*, and *equality in the distribution of roles* should be central. In addition, assessors should have experience with participatory research, show empathy, and be socially engaged.

In our view, the above results lead to the following main insights:

- There is a strong need for a **separate funding programme for bottom-up participatory research** that is more closely aligned with the real world than is often the case at present and that allows for iterations and flexibility throughout the process.
- Equality requires **attention to capacity building**, whereby attention to the different motivations of participants and investing in a good culture and structure of cooperation are of great importance (also in the long term).
- A follow-up programme should be approached as a **learning process** that involves citizen scientists in all phases of science funding and research, setting up funding experiments and a learning network.

5. Recommendations

We began this study with the question:

Under what conditions can citizens (organisations) and researchers collaborate in research projects in a (more) equal manner?

To answer this question, we conducted a desk research, interviews with experienced experts, three social lab sessions and a survey. We tested the insights and recommendations from the research and the sessions with members of the community of citizen scientists and participatory researchers, as well as with NWO.

During the process, it became increasingly clear that a research funder such as the NWO plays a crucial role in shaping the right conditions for citizens (organisations) and researchers to collaborate in research projects in a (more) equal manner. In order to fulfil this role even better in the (near) future, we make the following recommendations:

1. **Formulate a clear vision of equal collaboration in participatory research together with citizen scientists.**
2. **Establish a separate funding programme for bottom-up participatory research and long-term funding (continuity budget).**
3. **Invest in capacity building to increase equality.**
4. **Recognise the different needs and wishes of citizen scientists and try to accommodate them.**
5. **As an organisation, adopt a continuously learning, evaluating and participatory approach when implementing the recommendations.**

Below, we further explain the recommendations with concrete suggestions.

1. **Together with citizen scientists, formulate a clear vision on equal collaboration in participatory research.**

Develop a **vision for the future** on supporting and facilitating equal research with and by citizens and other social actors. Explicitly state the associated values and principles on the basis of which funding and other forms of support should be designed. Build on the results of this process.

In this process, the participants' desired visions for the future overlapped considerably: a strong focus on the funding and **support of research for, by and with communities**. Make use of these desired visions of the future and underlying values and principles (in this process, the values of 'equality', 'accessibility', 'reciprocity', 'collaboration', 'openness' and 'sustainability' often emerged). These visions, values and principles can provide guidance when making choices and setting priorities for further promoting equal collaboration in participatory research.

Work on **clear definitions and explanations of the terms** you use and make it clear from which perspective you are thinking. This is important for themes such as equality and participatory research. For example, is it about citizen science, participatory action research, community-led research, or community-based research, more fundamental research, or a combination of different approaches? Make use of the visions and ideas gathered during this process and discuss them with the community or communities.

2. Ensure that there is a separate funding programme for bottom-up participatory research and long-term funding (continuity budget).

Fund research that **focuses on the problems and questions experienced by communities**. Link to existing initiatives, networks and collectives, for example through those involved in this process. In this way, the research and its results can also make a real contribution to the positive impact on the local environment and the experiences of communities.

Make the **funding as accessible as possible**, but keep an eye on networking and impact after the process. With phased funding, many different projects and initiatives can be developed. With a continuity budget and **long-term funding**, successful initiatives and collaborative relationships can be continued and valuable returns will not be lost.

These forms of funding require (much) greater flexibility in terms of the types of compensation offered, which must be tailored to the citizen scientists. It is important to provide citizens and communities with **meaningful compensation for their efforts** (not gift vouchers) or to remove barriers to participation. Also include funding for the preparation of an application (start-up phase).

NWO is bound by legislation and regulations (such as the NWO Act and NWO's subsidy scheme) that make it difficult to follow (some of) the above recommendations. **Identify the barriers and necessary changes in legislation and regulations and discuss them**. See **what is possible within the existing rules** and make use of different types of funding.

Apply assessment criteria that **focus on ethics** and participation and leave room in projects for **alternative forms of (scientific) output**.

Invest in **community building** with a long-term focus, just like foreign financiers such as OeAD's Sparkling Science programme and UKRI's community-led research programmes, so that projects are part of a larger whole. This allows them to be of greater added value to the community. In this way, you strengthen the community in a sustainable manner and prevent research fatigue – unlike with one-off approaches.

¹⁸<https://oead.at/en/study-research-teaching/citizen-science/sparkling-science>

¹⁹<https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/public-engagement/research-and-innovation-for-everyone/>

3. Invest in capacity building to increase equality.

Invest in **training and further specify the skills needed** for equal cooperation in participatory research. In our project, particular interest was shown in training for research skills for citizens and participation skills for researchers and members of assessment committees. In addition, there was a need for training courses to develop facilitation skills, such as dealing with tensions and power differences in collaborations and how to address the different motivations of those involved. Facilitation for such collaborations is a profession in itself. Invest in this, as well as in the time needed to bring different voices together and speak the same language.

Focus the programmes and training courses on **increasing the agency and research capacity of citizen scientists**. Ensure that communities of researchers and citizens themselves learn from equal collaboration in participatory research projects, among other things by disseminating knowledge within and between communities in collaboration with networks such as Citizen Science NL and umbrella organisations around citizen collectives such as *Collectieve Kracht*.

Investigate the **social and technical infrastructures** required for equal participatory research, such as workshops for citizen scientists and publication opportunities for citizens. Specify what further investments in social and technical infrastructures are needed to facilitate encounters and joint knowledge production and exchange. Which investments need to be made with which minimum requirements, and which priorities need to be set?

Invest in **programmes for networking and connect yourself to existing networks**. Work together with existing intermediary organisations such as municipalities, libraries and neighbourhood groups. These types of stakeholders can take on the role of intermediary, enabling you to better connect with the existing context and the needs and ambitions (not just problems) that exist in the local community.

In addition to participatory research in funding programmes, focus on **scaling up and contributing to local communities**. Also investigate at institutional level what is needed to enable equal collaborations in participatory research and which structural issues, such as publication pressure, currently stand in the way of more equal cooperation.

Collect and aggregate the processes of research projects by **providing insight into the knowledge development** that is taking place, how this influences communities and how this translates into different transition scenarios towards further democratisation of science.

4. Recognise the different needs and wishes of citizen scientists and try to accommodate them.

Organise different moments and ways to **involve citizen scientists in decisions** at each stage of funding. Ensure that citizen scientists are not only involved in a separate programme but that the discussion also covers how they can be involved more structurally.²⁰

Communicate in clear and accessible language before, during and after a process, allowing sufficient room for responses and attention to different needs.

²⁰ See the results of social lab 2 for details of how different actors are involved in different phases of the research and funding process. In Pulskens, B., Cohen, J. B. & de Sterke, P., (2025). Social labs report Preliminary phase Citizen Science (in Dutch). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17100284>

Be **open to the diversity** of needs and experiences at all levels (participants' backgrounds, types of knowledge and experience, philosophical views on science, geographical locations, etc.). Where possible, link up with existing initiatives where a great deal of experience with participatory research is already in place and where rich networks have already been built up. This requires trust in the process and the courage to take steps into the unknown. Here, the outcomes, the type of research projects and the type of participants are not entirely predictable in advance and may be surprising or unexpected.

Recognise the **different needs and wishes of citizen scientists** by organising sufficient and regular opportunities for discussion with representatives of the community or communities.

5. As an organisation, adopt a continuously learning, evaluating and participatory approach in implementing the recommendations.

Learn from new funding programmes and support initiatives by **reflecting jointly as funders, citizen scientists and researchers** on the impact and possible areas for improvement. Use, for example, the methodology of reflexive monitoring in action as an approach.

Continue to **develop new funding methods** by learning from good examples of research programmes, collectives and funders at home and abroad. Support **exchange within funding programmes and at the institutional level** (both among funders and knowledge institutions and between them).

To this end, set up learning structures to organise learning processes with strong mutual exchange.

A prerequisite for the success of a continuous learning, evaluation and participatory approach is that sufficient capacity is made available for NWO employees, applicants or external parties and that they are directly involved in the learning process from the start in order to safeguard insights and follow-up actions.

²¹ van Mierlo, B., Regeer, B., Van Amstel, M., Arkesteijn, M., Beekman, V., Bunders, J., et al., 2010b Reflexive Monitoring in Action: a Guide for Monitoring System Innovation Projects. Boxpress, Oisterwijk, The Netherlands.

²² Potjer, S. (2019), *Experimental governance. From possible to feasible to commonplace innovation*. Utrecht: Urban Futures Studio, Utrecht University

